

Implementation of PUS fitness gymnastics in an effort to prevent stunting

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Abstract

Kuliah Kerja Mahasiswa (KKM) are a tangible manifestation of the duties of lecturers and students in implementing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, namely the aspect of service. Through community service activities (PKM) in Kebonpedes village, there is a synergy between universities and the community as a form of knowledge democracy. Stunting is a health problem that is still widely encountered in various regions. Stunting can threaten the quality of human resources in the future in the long term. The stunting prevalence rate in 2023 in Indonesia is 21,6 percent, which shows that stunting in Indonesia is still a problem with a moderate category. The purpose of this community service is to implement PUS fitness gymnastics in an effort to prevent stunting to improve health and prevent anemia. The method used is to provide health understanding and the implementation of fitness gymnastics which is one of the activities that can prevent stunting. The implementation of PKM through KKM received good enthusiasm from the participants, and full support from the head of the cadre for the implementation of this program, where the cadre mothers were looking forward to the presence of the KKM team. The outcomes of the activity can foster habits and understanding of the importance of fitness as part of alternatives to prevent stunting. Suggestions, PKM activities and further assistance are still considered necessary.

Keywords: PUS fitness exercises; prevent stunting

Introduction

Gymnastics is one of the sports that involves several body movements and requires speed, strength, and harmony of physical movements. Various gymnastics certainly have their own benefits for the health of the body, if you do it regularly every type of gymnastics, it will make the body more ideal, so that it can make you appear more confident. Gymnastics aims to train the body by performing certain movements deliberately, consciously and strategically, and is carried out systematically. Gymnastics is also one of the sports that can be done to prevent stunting, gymnastics is a type of exercise that is very light to do and has many benefits such as training the muscles in the body, maintaining heart health and helping to release stress. People who are involved in gymnastics will develop their muscle endurance, strength, power, flexibility, coordination, agility, and balance. Especially if it is balanced with activities that require the work of the heart and lungs (cardio-vascular system). By doing exercise regularly, it will make health and physical development good and balanced.

Stunting is a serious global problem. It is currently estimated to have occurred in more than 160 million children under five years worldwide and if not treated properly, it is estimated that by 2025 there will be an additional 127 million stunted children in the world. The problem of stunting also occurs in Indonesia. Based on the results of the Indonesian Nutrition Status Survey (SSGI), although it managed to decrease by around 2.8 percent compared to 2021, the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia in 2022 is still at 21.6 percent. This figure is still considered high, considering that WHO targets the stunting rate to be no more than 20 percent. The prevalence of stunting is a big problem because it is a threat to long-term national welfare and resilience.

According to “Peraturan Presiden (Perpres) Republik Indonesia Nomor 72 Tahun 2021” concerning the acceleration of the handling of Stunting, what is meant by stunting is a disorder of child growth and development caused by chronic malnutrition and repeated infections. This disorder is characterized by a different height below the standard set by health materials. Stunting is divided into two categories. The first is stunting, namely toddlers whose z-score is less than -3.00 Standard Deviation. In other words, Stunting is a long-term malnutrition in infants in the first 1000 days of life and causes the development and growth of the child's brain to be hampered. As a result of malnutrition, stunted babies grow shorter than the standard height of all toddlers. However, it should be remembered that stunting is definitely short, while being short is not necessarily stunted.

According to WHO in 2018, the percentage of stunted toddlers was 150.8 million people or around 22.2% in 2017 globally (Sartorius *et al.*, 2020; Fibriasari *et al.*, 2021). The Asian region is the region with the largest percentage of stunted toddlers after Africa and for the Southeast Asian region as many as 25.7 million people which is the second highest region after South Asia. Meanwhile, Indonesia was ranked 6th for the number of stunted toddlers in 2013.

Kebonpedes Village is one of the villages located in the Kebonpedes District, Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province and is one of the villages indicated to be experiencing stunting. Based on health records in Kebonpedes Village in 2023 there were 22 stunted toddlers and this number decreased in 2024 to 19 stunted toddlers. Seeing the large number of stunting sufferers in Kebonpedes Village and the large number of fertile couples and pregnant women, we intend to carry out PUS Fitness Gymnastics activities and counseling on stunting prevention for productive mothers in the Kebonpedes Village area as an area indicated to be experiencing stunting. the importance of increasing public insight and understanding regarding stunting, increasing public awareness of the importance of preventing stunting. Seeing this, it is necessary to hold activities that support reducing the increase in stunting rates, in order to create healthy and well-nourished children.

KKM is an intracurricular activity that combines the implementation of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education with the method of providing learning and work experiences to students in community empowerment activities. One of the activities that improves critical thinking and experience for students in a real form is through the Student Work Lecture activity. The KKM program is an intracurricular course that must be taken by students in every study program at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education. KKM is a form of real work in the community to empower rural communities designed by students who are able to lead students to become

whole individuals with the guidance of lecturers, both in utilizing knowledge, the ability to analyze the conditions of the surrounding community, and providing solutions to overcome various social, economic, health, education, and political problems according to their field of knowledge.

Educational assistance activities at KKM aim to provide an understanding to the people of Kebonpedes Village, Sukabumi Regency about the importance of preventing stunting by doing fitness exercises. Therefore, the purpose of this community service is to carry out PUS fitness exercises in an effort to prevent stunting in order to improve health and prevent anemia.

Method

The method of implementing KKM activities is carried out by applying the observation approach, socialization, activity implementation stages and evaluation (e.g., Aulia *et al.*, 2023; Yunus *et al.*, 2024; Husni *et al.*, 2023; Susetyo *et al.*, 2023; Rizky *et al.*, 2023; Supriatna *et al.*, 2023; Nurmilah *et al.*, 2023; Hadi *et al.*, 2024; Husni *et al.*, 2023; and Julianti *et al.*, 2023). The implementation of activities in the sub-theme of community service by students who are members of the KKM team consists of physical fitness gymnastics activities. The method used in this activity is preventive action with direct community education about preventing stunting in women of childbearing age including women of childbearing age, pregnant women and mothers of toddlers. The implementation of community service activities was carried out at the Sawala Building, Kebonpedes Village on May 18, 2024. Before carrying out the activity, the team first took care of the implementation permit through the Head of the Kebonpedes Village Cadre. The agreed schedule for determining the implementation is May 18, 2024 at the Sawala Building, Kebonpedes Village at 07.00 - 09.00 (western indonesia time, WIB).

Fig. 1. Implementation of healthy gymnastics activities

Results

Implementation of activities

Participants who took part in gymnastics activities were Kebonpedes village cadres, gymnastics was carried out at around 08 o'clock; 00 am and warmed up first for five minutes. The gymnastics received a positive response, participants were also very enthusiastic and participated in stunting prevention fitness gymnastics activities. The gymnastics was guided by two KKM students and other KKM members participated in the gymnastics lineup that we carried out.

Results and evaluation of the results of the implementation of activities

Community service activities by carrying out fitness gymnastics activities to prevent stunting in productive women. Gymnastics participants were followed by Kebonpedes village cadres Before the activity started, participants were given a direct explanation about stunting and after that participants warmed up before gymnastics for 5 minutes. It is hoped that this fitness gymnastics activity can prevent stunting.

The implementation of PKM through KKM received good enthusiasm from the participants, and full support from the head of the cadre for the implementation of this program, where the cadre mothers were eagerly awaiting the presence of the KKM team. We gained a lot of experience from the gymnastics activities, starting from how we should be able to interact with the cadre mothers who have various characters. This is because the implementation of KKM received a fairly good response, seen from the very active response given. In addition, the output also greatly appreciates the program that has been given by KKM students because this program has a big impact, namely the closer the students are to the cadre mothers and can also add experience that is directly in the surrounding environment, which of course will be experienced by education students in the future.

Discussion

Stunting not only affects physical growth, but also affects a child's cognitive development. Children who experience stunting tend to be shorter and are at risk of delays in achieving their cognitive and social potential. The main characteristic of stunting is a child's height that is shorter than it should be for their age. This measurement is often measured by the child growth index. Children who experience stunting may have a weight that is disproportionate to their height, giving the impression of being thin. Stunting can affect a child's brain and cognitive development, which can affect their ability to learn and understand. Children who experience stunting may have low immunity, making them more susceptible to disease and infection.

Lack of balanced nutritional intake, especially during early growth, can be a major trigger for stunting. Infections and infectious diseases that often occur in children can inhibit nutrient absorption, thereby exacerbating the risk of stunting. Economic and social factors, such as

unequal access to education and health services, can also cause stunting. Supplemental feeding programs and nutritional education can help improve nutritional intake in children.

The implementation of the KKM activity with the theme of fitness gymnastics was quite well received, as seen from the very active response given. In addition, the output also greatly appreciates the program that has been given by KKM students because this program has a big impact on bringing students closer to cadre mothers and can also add direct experience in the surrounding environment, which of course will be experienced by education students in the future. The output from the results of the activity can foster habits and understanding of the importance of being fond of sports as an alternative to preventing stunting.

Conclusion

The implementation of PKM through KKM received good enthusiasm from the participants, and full support from the head of the cadre for the implementation of this program, where the cadre mothers were looking forward to the presence of the KKM team. The output of the activity results can foster habits and understanding of the importance of maintaining fitness as an alternative to preventing stunting. Suggestions, PKM activities and further assistance are still considered necessary.

Acknowledgments

Community service activities by carrying out fitness gymnastics activities to prevent stunting in productive women. Gymnastics participants were followed by Kebonpedes village cadres. Before the activity started, participants were given a direct explanation about stunting and after that participants warmed up before gymnastics for 5 minutes. It is hoped that this fitness gymnastics activity can prevent stunting.

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